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RIGOUROUS -
secuRe desIGn and deploYment of
trUsthwoRthy cOntinUum computing 6G
Services

Deliverable 6.1

PROJECT WEBSITE

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable provides an overview of the newly created web page of RIGOUROUS. The web page includes several functionalities such as different tabs containing several information about the project background, objectives, structure and outcomes, deliverables or related news. The main objective is to show that the webpage is active and works with no errors, as well as testing the different functionalities.

2 INTRODUCTION

The document is structured in a list of chapters. In each one, we show the information and functionalities included in each of the available pages or tabs, through a series of screenshots and some explanatory text. By last, a conclusions, references and list of figures sections can be found.

3 MAIN PAGE

In first place, Figures 1 to 4 show the main page contents. Above, the project title is found. The “Learn more” button, that can be found multiple times in this first page, redirects the user to the “Planning” tab, where further information can be retrieved (see Chapter 4). After it, a section with three main keywords (Cybersecurity, Privacy and Trust) is included. The section with the “Core areas”, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Main page screenshot (1)

Figure 2. Main page screenshot (2)

Below this, there are some sections (Figure 3) which depict the focus of the project, mission statement and the lifecycle used: DevSecOps. A better image management has addressed this issue in two way: (1) acquired higher-quality assets from open-license stock photos libraries; (2) retuned our image delivery optimization plugin (Optimole) to deliver higher quality assets whenever network conditions allow to (i.e., now defaults to 90% compression in the AVIF codec).

Figure 3. Main page screenshot (3)

In the bottom of the page, the project call name and some logos are also included. The footer as is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Main page footer screenshot

4 PLANNING TAB

In the planning tab, as we said previously in Chapter 3, further information of the project can be found. The page contents with that information can be consulted in Figures 5 to 7. We can find the main objectives of the project, innovations, structure containing the different work packages, the leader of each one and the starting and end months. By last, the project outcomes are also included at the end.

Similarly to the main page, we now include higher quality assets (whenever possible, for instance we do not have available a higher quality version of the diagram shown in Figure 5). Simultaneous, the image delivery optimization plugin now defaults to much higher quality.

Planning

The RIGOROUS project aspires to identify and address the major cybersecurity, trust and privacy risks threatening the network, devices, computing infrastructure, and next generation of services

High Level Objectives

- ✓ Holistic Smart Service framework for securing the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum lifecycle management
- ✓ Human-Centric DevSecOps
- ✓ Model-based and AI-driven Automated Security Orchestration, Trust Management and deployment
- ✓ Advanced AI-driven Anomaly Detection, decision and Mitigation Strategies
- ✓ Demonstration of a Set of Industrially Relevant Use Cases in Operational Environments

The diagram illustrates the project's architecture, showing a flow from DESIGN to OPERATION. The DESIGN phase includes Understanding users and Security goals and requirements. The OPERATION phase includes CONTROL, SECURITY, ORCHESTRATION AND MANAGEMENT, and SECURITY PLANE. The SECURITY PLANE is divided into IOT, Substrata, Edge, Core, and Cloud, all supported by 5G Infrastructure.

Figure 5. Planning tab screenshot (1)

-

Promoting an open strategic autonomy by leading the development of key digital, enabling, and emerging technologies, sectors, and value chains
-

Making Europe the first digitally led circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy
-

Foster Europe's technological leadership in digital technologies and in future emerging enabling technologies, by strengthening European capacities in key parts of digital and future supply chains, allowing agile responses to urgent needs, and by investing in early discovery and industrial uptake of new technologies

Innovations & Advancement

- ✓ Intent-based Security & Privacy Formal Modelling and Onboarding Specification
- ✓ AI-based Security Orchestration across Network Segments
- ✓ Privacy-preserving AI for Anomaly Detection in B5G
- ✓ End-to-End Multidomain 6G Slicing over Zero-touch Security Network Management
- ✓ 6G Zero Trust Security Adaptations
- ✓ Continuum SOAR Loop Reaction and Mitigation
- ✓ IoT Device Bootstrapping and Trusted Application Onboarding

Figure 6. Planning tab screenshot (2)

Work Structure

Expected Outcomes

- ✓ Identification/characterization of the threat landscape applied to the envisioned end-to-end 6G connectivity and service systems and of the technologies and architecture to mitigate them.
- ✓ Availability of technologies supporting the necessary levels of trustworthiness, resilience, openness, transparency, and dependability expected under the EU regulations (such as GDPR and Cyber Security Act, including associated provisions including new certification processes etc) across a complete continuum incorporating the human-cyber-physical system including connectivity-service provision.

Figure 7. Planning tab screenshot (3)

5 DELIVERABLES TAB

The deliverables tab (Figure 8) contains a table, which is empty at the moment as no deliverables have been done yet, with relevant information of each one of them: identifier (ID), Delivery Name (this should be replaced with “Deliverable name”), Editor and Month. The Delivery Name will be a hyperlink pointed to a download page.

Figure 8. Deliverables tab screenshot

6 DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION TAB

The dissemination & exploitation tab (Figure 9) will contain all the relevant information related to publications (conference, journal and workshop articles, and project presentations) and important events that are divided into past and future events, which is very appropriate.

Figure 9. Dissemination & exploitation tab screenshot

7 CONTACT TAB

This tab (Figures 10 and 11) contains the contact information (name, affiliation and contact e-mail) of the project coordinator, which for this project is Antonio Skarmeta from University of Murcia. In addition, below, the logos of all the participants or partners are included, but no contact information is shown for any of them. This is adequate since all inquiries should be sent firstly to the project coordinator, so contact information about the partners is not necessary.

Figure 10. Contact tab screenshot (1)

Consortium

Figure 11. Contact tab screenshot (2)

8 NEWS TAB

By last, there is the news tab, where all the news related to the project will be posted. As can be seen in Figures 12 and 13, at the moment a hello world article has been included, with introductory information about the project and the website.

Figure 12. News tab screenshot (1)

We are the SNS RIGOUROUS European project!

This website is the first step towards making our work public.

Stay tuned for further developments!

Search

Recent Posts

[Hello World!](#)

Figure 13. Hello world new screenshot

9 SOCIAL MEDIA

The different social media profiles can be accessed directly through the website using the icons located at the right upper corner. In Figures 14 to 17, the profiles (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and Youtube) are shown. The information contained in each one of them is enough considering the early stage of the project. There is a “view profile” button that allows the user to visit the profile normally. We completed all Twitter validation procedures after the incorrect flagging of our account.

Figure 14. Twitter profile screenshot

Figure 15. Facebook profile screenshot

Figure 16. LinkedIn profile screenshot

Figure 17. Youtube profile screenshot

10 BACKEND DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

In this section we detail the infrastructure and technical decisions behind the website.

10.1. Content Management System (CMS)

We have chosen Wordpress to be our Content Management System (CMS), due to its easiness and flexibility in handling direct community interactions (e.g., comments and content contributed by users) and the plethora of plugins to extend functionality quickly. The flipside to using wordpress is the need to maintain a PHP-based CMS that is known for having some vulnerable plugins that may compromise the website or even the system(s) in that infrastructure should the vulnerability lead to further escalation.

Figure 18. Management dashboard

Figure 19. WYSIWYG Editor for easy content creation

10.2. Webhosting architecture

The website is hosted on-premises at the Instituto de Telecomunicações – Aveiro datacenter, within a Proxmox cluster that hosts (at the moment) two VMs. The first VM is the endpoint and has a public IP to receive incoming traffic. The second VM has a Docker environment where the Wordpress CMS is instantiated. We can scale this system as needed, on-demand, according to the load. We can do so vertically (add more resources to the same VMs) or horizontally (distribute load across more VMs). The first is less desirable because it may impose some downtime, while the second is our antecipated solution to cope with demand, having the endpoint act as load balancer.

10.3. Risk and Threat Management

We have our DNS hosted at Cloudflare and also leverage the various caching, Content Delivery Network (CDN), firewalling, Web Application Filtering (WAF), and other integrations provided.

We have Cloudflare’s built-in reporting to track attempted attacks (i.e., known patterns), throttle access to the login page, and advisories on how to react to recorded incidents.

11 CONCLUSIONS

As described along the document, the website is active, functional, contains a good amount of information and functionalities. During the launch of the website some issue were addressed helping to improve the overall behaviour and appearance of the website.

12 REFERENCES

[1] RIGOUROUS project. RIGOUROUS: secuRe desIGN and depLOyment of trUsthwoRthy cOntinUum computing 6G Services. Retrieved March 7, 2023, from rigorous.eu

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